

AUTOMATIC BOOK VENDING MACHINE

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ABSTRACT

Possibility of having good knowledge is closely linked to availability of the study materials mainly book. If books are not available on time it may affect the results. According to our survey students who live at collage hostels may need books any time irrespective to the library time. Collage liberty provide books on at the own working hours i.e 10 to 5 which is only 7 hr a day so books to the students will only be issued during this hours. Availability of books make access to the information which should not be limited by any time limits. So,we have come up with a major solution over this problem. We have developed a machine that will deliver books 24/7 any time. The lack of book supply leads to less understanding. Our “Automatic Book Vending Machine” can provide books any time. Although it is not a new concept in its entirety. It can prove to be useful and hence could be important in our developing country.

INTRODUCTION

Now a day in this fast world appliances which are completely automatic are preferred. Which is one of the most important advantage of this project. This system is controlled by a microcontroller. Automatic vending machine decentralised book distribution system that provides computer controls storage, dispensing and tracking of books have been recommended as one potential mechanism to improve availability and less human interference in the system and this machine are widely used in many libraries and book stores. There is no doubt that this machine can enhance the efficiency of book delivering, but the capacity to deliver the boom at any time Automatic dispense machine provide secure book storage in book stores and libraries. Along with the tracking of book borrower’s data. Automatic book vending machine enhances the availability of the book to the borrower and facilizes the linearly administration of the book by increasing their accessibility on library.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Bock Diagram:

A. MICROCONTROLLER

In this project we are using 89S52 microcontroller. It programmed using keil Software. Which provide effective environment for performing the task.

B. DISPENSER BOX

It is made of steel cabinet which hold the delivered books. Books are sided in to the dispenser box with the help of stepper motor. Just like other vending machine it also employs security flaps at the opening of the dispenser box

C. USER Authentication

User authentication is depend on the application of the machine if it is to be placed at book stores then it is not important to identify the user just need to vend the book. But when it comes to library system machine is needed to be filled with library data that helps the machine to identify the user, there are several technologies to identify the user

1. Login Id and Password

This is one of the most trusted way. Library provides each user a unique id and password so they can get access to the machine by logging in.

FLOWCHART

RESULT

From this concept we can conclude that the automatic book vending machine is technically flexible to the students. It is based on microcontroller. It gives availability of the book all the time and also in rural areas it is very helpful and gives ease access. As well as economical as compared to vending machines available in market. And can be easily modified for future expansion.

REFERENCE

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